

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

Hybrid theoretical models for molecular nanoplasmonics

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The multidisciplinary nature of the research in molecular nanoplasmonics, i.e. the use of plasmonic nanostructures to enhance, control or suppress properties of molecules interacting with light, led to contributions from different theory communities over the years, with the aim to understand, interpret and predict the physical and chemical phenomena occurring at the molecular- and nano-scale in presence of light. Multiscale hybrid techniques, using a different level of description for the molecule and the plasmonic nanosystems, permit a reliable representation of the atomistic details and of collective features, like plasmons, in such complex systems. Here we focus on a selected set of topics of current interest in molecular plasmonics (control of electronic excitations in light harvesting systems, polaritonic chemistry, hot carrier generation and plasmon-enhanced catalysis). We discuss how their description may benefit from a hybrid modeling approach and what are the main challenges for the application of such models. In doing so, we also provide an introduction to such models and to the selected topics, as well as general discussions on their theoretical descriptions.

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Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

I. INTRODUCTION

The interaction between light and composite systems at the nanoscale ignited over the years the interest of different scientific communities¹⁻⁷, attracted by the multidisciplinary nature of the topic, and by the simultaneous fundamental and technological implications associated to this research field.

The individual components of these systems can be single molecules and nanostructures, possibly aggregated in nano- or even mesoscopic assemblies. As a result of the mutual interaction between the various elements of the system, chemical and physical properties of the composite system can largely differ from those of the single components, and the light-induced response can strongly deviate from the sum of the responses of each constituent.

More specifically, one class of phenomena which has been extensively studied and, at the same time, is still characterized by a number of open questions, is that related to the molecular nanoplasmonics.⁸ Namely, molecular nanoplasmonics investigates how plasmon-induced processes modify the properties of a molecular system close to a metal nanoparticle (NP).

NP plasmon effects are used to strongly modify the spectroscopic signal of molecules interacting with it^{9,10}. Outcomes of plasmon-enhanced spectroscopy then depend on the shape and nature of the NP, on the geometric configuration of the NP+molecule(s) system^{8,11,12}, and on the type of applied external pulse¹³. Examples of plasmon-based experimental techniques and phenomena are: surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS)^{14,15}, in which the molecular Raman signal is enhanced by several orders of magnitude; plasmon-modified (enhanced or quenched, according to the relative molecular orientation with respect to the NP) molecular fluorescence^{16,17}; photochemical reactions, which can be altered by plasmon-assisted mechanisms^{5,18}, as hot-carrier (HC) generation and transfer from NP to the molecule⁴, and the strong coupling in plasmonic nanocavities containing the molecule, which leads to hybrid light-matter states^{19,20}.

The theoretical modeling of systems of such an intrinsic complexity requires a multiscale description, that is able to capture the individual and collective behaviour of the composite system. Focusing on the molecular nanoplasmonics^{8,21-28}, the requirement of a multiscale hybrid approach arises naturally: the small subsystem, i.e. the single molecule or the molecular aggregate, and the larger component, i.e. the nanostructure, need to be described by means of different approaches. the level of description is adapted according to

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

the different size and level of accuracy required/affordable. Hybrid methods for molecular plasmonics can be categorized based on the level of theory for the molecular target and on the description of the plasmonic nanostructure. Considering the molecular target, we can distinguish three main categories, ordered in terms of increasing complexity: (i) classical polarizable point dipole models ("dip" in the rest of this work),^{22,29-34} where the molecule is characterized only by a frequency-dependent polarizability tensor (often isotropic); (ii) two-level quantum mechanical models ("2lev" from now on), a model derived from quantum optics where the molecule is described as a quantum system with two states (ground and excited),⁷ separated by a certain excitation energy and coupled through a transition dipole, possibly obtained from empirical data; (iii) fully atomistic models based on a quantum chemistry description ("QM", to comply with the standard acronyms of hybrid quantum chemistry models),^{2,6,11,12,24-28,35-46} providing chemical details and predictive power. The present classification is somewhat rough, and in particular for polaritonic chemistry the 2lev model has been extended to include the dependence on one or a few nuclear coordinates to model photochemistry.⁴⁷

NP can be seen as an effective environment interacting with and responding to the external electromagnetic field and the molecular probe. An accurate representation of NP, in terms of atomic and electronic structure and dynamics, is often not necessary, and modeling the NP response, as a whole, by classical methods is indeed a reliable approach^{2,6,35}. When combined with the QM description of the molecule, such hybrid approaches are called QM/classical. A full QM description of the nanosystem is limited by the computationally accessible size of the system (a few nanometers), and perhaps it is also not needed in many cases, judging from the good quality of the classical electromagnetic descriptions of the optical properties of metal NPs.⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰ Such hybrid approaches permit to successfully study plasmon-induced phenomena involving molecules, as plasmon-spectroscopy (SERS, fluorescence etc.) and plasmon-modified chemical reactions.

QM/classical approaches can be further classified by following the modeling of the NP:⁶ QM/continuum, in which the NP is defined as a continuum characterized by a dielectric function^{11,12,27,36,38-42,45,46} and QM/discrete, in which a discrete, atomistic but classical description of the NP is adopted^{24-26,28,37,43,44}.

QM/continuum models can be seen as extension of continuum solvation models, that were proposed in literature over the years, as the polarizable continuum (PCM) model^{51,52}. The

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

NP is in fact treated as a finite dielectric medium, with a given size, shape and nature, and it is characterized by a frequency-dependent permittivity function $\epsilon(\omega)$. The ϵ function describes the NP electromagnetic response to the external field and generated by the electronic density of the molecule close to the NP. QM/continuum approaches were originally defined in the frequency domain, i.e., considering monochromatic external perturbations, usually coupled to a density functional theory (DFT) and a time-dependent DFT (TDDFT) description of the molecule.^{11,21,36} Recent developments extended the QM/continuum models to the time domain^{13,53}, allowing one to directly simulate time-resolved (plasmon-enhanced) spectroscopies.

Analogously, QM/discrete approaches can be seen as extension of QM/MM approaches to molecular plasmonics.⁶ Here a proper description of the response of the NP atoms to external electromagnetic field have been developed in terms of atomic polarizabilities and capacitances (the Discrete Interaction Model of Jensen and coworkers,^{37,54} and the model by Rinkevicius et al.⁴³) and by a discretized version of Drude model, as in the ω FQ approach.^{55,56}

In addition to the QM molecule and the NP, other components of the systems may also require to be modeled. For example, a solvent that embeds both molecule and NP is often included as an additional dielectric in QM/continuum models (QM/discrete models have mostly been applied to solvent free environment). The complexity of some molecules, such as light harvesting complexes in proteins, has prompted the extension of QM/continuum models to a three-layer description:⁶ QM for the protein chromophores, classical atomistic molecular mechanics for the protein scaffold and a continuum description for the NP and the surrounding solvent⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹.

QM/classical models have been originally devised for (and so far mostly applied to) spectroscopy, such as SERS^{54,60,61} (and its non-linear extension Surface Enhanced Hyper Raman scattering),⁶² plasmon-modified molecular fluorescence,^{11,63} Surface Enhanced Infrared Absorption (SEIRA),⁶⁴ Excitation Energy Transfer,⁶⁵ Surface Enhanced Two-Photon Absorption.⁶⁶ Moreover, all of these phenomena have been investigated within a traditional quantum chemistry picture, considering response theory in the frequency domain and neglecting decoherence effects. Based on this *status quo*, we decided to focus this Perspective on a few subtopics of molecular plasmonics -different from spectroscopies- that are rapidly developing and of broad interest, and that also represent active fields of research of our

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

group. We shall in particular discuss the potential usefulness of QM/continuum models to treat such topics, the status of their application and the theoretical challenges to be overcome for their practical applications. Moreover, we shall also review recent developments in QM/continuum modeling that allows to embrace a natively time-dependent picture of molecular nanoplasmonics,⁵³ including quantum decoherence effects.¹³ Such picture is in fact one of the ingredient to tackle some of the forefront molecular nanoplasmonics subtopics just mentioned.

More in detail, the following discussion will focus on (Figure 1): the interplay between plasmonic and decoherence effects on the optical properties of molecules^{13,67} and light-harvesting complexes^{58,59}, the strong-coupling regime between light and matter for molecules in plasmonic nanocavities^{19,68} and its relation with polaritonic chemistry^{47,69–72} and the problem of HC generation and dynamics in NPs and their injection into close molecules^{73–75}, as well as the role of HCs in plasmon-enhanced catalytic reactions.⁷⁶

Each topic is discussed starting by a short introduction and overview of the state-of-the-art, followed by a description of the main theoretical approaches applied to the topic, open challenges for QM/continuum models and possible future developments. In particular, Section III A reports on using plasmon-based processes to control excitations in light-harvesting systems, and discuss the role of coherence; molecule-plasmon strong coupling is presented in Section III B; the modeling of HC generation, dynamics and injection into molecules from plasmonic NPs is treated in Section III C; how theory and simulations can help in the understanding of plasmon-enhanced catalysis is shown in Section III D. We focus our discussion on QM/continuum models, whose basic concepts and relevant recent developments are reviewed in Section II.

II. BASIC FEATURES OF QM/CONTINUUM MODELS

In this Section we introduce the main features of QM/continuum models.^{11,12,27,36,38–42,45,46} We start presenting their traditional formulation (i.e., in the frequency domain), and then discuss the extension to time domain. We discuss in particular the model that has been dubbed PCM-NP (to underline its conceptual relation with PCM)⁶, whose foundation was laid almost 20 years ago.³⁶

FIG. 1. Graphical summary of the molecular-nanoplasmonics topics discussed in the Perspective.

A. QM/continuum models: frequency domain

Within QM/continuum models, the NP is represented as a continuous body characterized by its response properties to electric fields, i.e. the external field and that generated by a neighboring QM charge distribution: a conductor for static perturbations and a dielectric characterized by a frequency-dependent complex permittivity $\epsilon(\omega)$ for time-dependent perturbations. In the quasistatic limit, the electrostatic potential (or field) resulting from the polarization of the NP is solution of a Poisson equation with proper boundary conditions³⁶. The molecular system is instead described at QM level of theory.

A general approach to simulate the NP response is to define a set of apparent charges (AC) \mathbf{q} on the surface of the NP, which is discretized in terms of a mesh of elements, called tesserae. This choice ensures an excellent compromise between accuracy and computational cost. No specific limitation due to the NP shape is given. Each tessera is characterized by

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

a representative position and area. The \mathbf{q} charges are described by complex numbers. The AC technique is numerically implemented by using the boundary element method (BEM). BEM has been successfully employed in the classical description of plasmonic fields originating from general-shaped NPs in the presence of an external field and/or in the proximity of a system treated at a quantum level.⁶ In these conditions, NPs polarize as a response to an external field (external polarization) and to the perturbed quantum mechanical electron density (molecular polarization), providing in turn a polarization field to the quantum system⁵¹. Within such formulation, the induced charges are written in terms of the total polarizing potential (\mathbf{V}), sum of the external and molecular contributions, computed at the tesserae position:

$$\mathbf{q}(\omega) = \mathbf{Q}(\omega) \mathbf{V}(\omega), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}(\omega)$ is the frequency-dependent response matrix, which depends on the NP surface tesserae (hence, on the NP geometry) and NP dielectric properties⁶. The $\epsilon(\omega)$ function is typically taken by experimental data, possibly corrected for the limited mean free path of electrons in the nanoparticle.⁷⁷

Within PCM-NP, the continuum model for the NP systems were successfully coupled to HF/TDHF and then DFT/TDDFT^{11,12,36,78}. Linear-response TDDFT⁷⁹ provides important information on excited states, such as its decomposition in terms of single-particle transitions. Recently developed algorithms, based on an approximate method to compute the absorption spectrum from the imaginary part of dynamic polarizability^{80,81}, allow one to overcome the computational burden when looking at the high-energy part of the spectrum⁸².

B. QM/continuum models: time domain

In order to provide an accurate and physically meaningful description of the fast and ultrafast phenomena occurring when a NP (or a nanocavity) and a molecular system mutually interact with an external electromagnetic field, a time-resolved approach becomes mandatory. Focusing on ultrafast electronic processes, a time-domain QM/continuum model has to properly describe the time evolution of the molecular density, via the appropriate formulation of the time-dependent Schrödinger equation, and of the coupled set of ACs, using a

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

FIG. 2. Scheme representation of a time-resolved QM/continuum model applied to molecular plasmonics.

classical electromagnetic solver.

A computationally convenient time-resolved version of BEM has been recently proposed^{53,83}, where the set of ACs, now time-dependent ($\mathbf{q}(t)$), can be formally obtained by Fourier transforming Eq. (1),

$$\mathbf{q}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \mathbf{Q}(t-t') \mathbf{V}(t') dt'. \quad (2)$$

This makes the time-resolved BEM a powerful tool for describing the time evolution of a quantum system interacting with a NP, giving rise to a model that can be dubbed TD-PCM-NP. An alternative approach to BEM is given by the finite difference time domain solver, coupled to real-time TDDFT^{40,42,84,85}.

In what follows we will focus on the quasistatic limit, but it is worth reminding here that the full coupling between a QM molecule and a dielectric (e.g., a NP) within BEM formulations has also been developed⁸⁶.

Within the TD-PCM-NP, the time-dependent Schrödinger equation of the subsystem of interest, $|\Psi_S(t)\rangle$, is propagated using the time-dependent Schrödinger equation

$$i \frac{d}{dt} |\Psi_S(t)\rangle = \hat{H}_S(t) |\Psi_S(t)\rangle, \quad (3)$$

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

with

$$\hat{H}_S(t) = \hat{H}_0 - \vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{E}_{ext}(t) + \hat{H}_{pol}, \quad (4)$$

where \hat{H}_0 is the field-free electronic Hamiltonian, $\vec{\mu}$ is the system dipole, and \hat{H}_{pol} is polarization interaction term

$$\hat{H}_{pol}(t) = \mathbf{q}(t) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{V}}, \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{V}}$ is the generic electrostatic potential operator evaluated at the NP surface representative points. The electrostatic potential, which polarizes the NP, originates from the external field $\vec{E}_{ext}(t)$ and from the molecular density. Examples of \hat{H}_{pol} will be given in Section III A and III D for different systems.

The time-dependent system wavefunction $|\Psi_S(t)\rangle$ is expanded using the eigenstate basis $\{|\lambda\rangle\}$ of \hat{H}_0 ^{13,53,87}

$$|\Psi_S(t)\rangle = \sum_{\lambda} C_{\lambda}(t)|\lambda\rangle, \quad (6)$$

with λ running over the electronic eigenstates, and $C_{\lambda}(t)$ are time-dependent coefficients evolving according to the Hamiltonian $\hat{H}_S(t)$.

Relaxation (i.e., decay of an electronic excited state to the ground state) and dephasing (i.e., the loss of quantum coherence between the superimposed molecular states) has been recently enclosed in TD-PCM-NP by means of the theory of open quantum systems⁸⁸ (Figure 3). Decoherence of the quantum state can strongly affect the spectroscopic response of the system^{13,87,89,90}, because the timescales of the relevant physical processes for nanophotonics (from few to hundreds of fs) are those of the typical electronic and vibronic dephasing⁹¹. Such implementation^{13,87} is based on the stochastic formulation of the time-dependent Schrödinger equation (SSE)^{92,93}, originally developed within the field of quantum optics^{94,95}. SSE implements the physics of open quantum systems using the system wave function, instead of the density matrix used in master-equation formalism^{96,97}. The SSE in the Markovian limit is given by^{87,93}:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} |\Psi_S(t)\rangle = \hat{H}_S(t) |\Psi_S(t)\rangle + \sum_q^M l_q(t) \hat{S}_q |\Psi_S(t)\rangle - \frac{i}{2} \sum_q^M \hat{S}_q^\dagger \hat{S}_q |\Psi_S(t)\rangle, \quad (7)$$

where \hat{S}_q describes the effect of the environment on the quantum system, through the M interaction channels q . The non-Hermitian term $-\frac{i}{2} \sum_q^M \hat{S}_q^\dagger \hat{S}_q$ describes the dissipation, whereas $\sum_q^M l_q(t) \hat{S}_q$ is the fluctuation, modeled by a Wiener process $l_q(t)$, both generated

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

FIG. 3. System and environment separation within the theory of open systems, and a schematic representation of a SSE simulation and post-processing.

by the environment. The system coincides with the degrees of freedom which are explicitly treated at quantum level, as the electronic structure of a molecule, while the environment contains all the other degrees of freedom whose description is encoded in the dissipation and fluctuation terms. In the Markovian limit, the autocorrelation function of the environment is a δ function⁹⁸.

Populations and coherences of the states of the system at time t are extracted from the density matrix, $\hat{\rho}_S(t)$, obtained by averaging on the number of independent SSE realizations⁸⁷, as shown in Figure 3.

It should be remarked that in the application made so far of the SSE to TD-PCM-NP,¹³ the environment responsible for the \hat{S}_q terms is added on top of the dielectric environment (i.e., the NP), whose interaction with the molecule is instead treated deterministically following standard TD-PCM-NP. A further step to be accomplished is to move towards a multiscale approach where the NP is properly treated as part of the environment as defined in the theory of open quantum system: the correlation function of the environment will no longer be a δ function (as in the Markovian regime) but will be built from the time-dependent kernel of the non-Markovian SSE in terms of the time-dependent polarization of the NP.⁵³ Such formal connection has been recently developed in Ref. 99, but not implemented yet.

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

III. SELECTED MOLECULAR NANOPLASMONICS APPLICATIONS

In this section we discuss selected topics of current interest in molecular nanoplasmonics that may benefit from the application of QM/continuum models, as anticipated in the introduction. The order of the topics presentation reflects the maturity of QM/continuum models to treat each of them, leaving HC-induced photochemistry and plasmon-assisted catalysis at the end as they require the description of electron exchanges between molecule and plasmonic nanostructures, that is obviously a challenge when a classical, continuum description is used.

A. Enhanced light-harvesting by nanoplasmonics

A localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) of a NP can intensify light scattering and enhance light concentration around the structure, creating a so called hot spot.^{100–104} As a consequence, for instance, the fluorescence of an emitting system placed in such localized hot spots can be greatly increased as a result of the enhancement of the excitation field and of radiative rate modifications, that increases the effective quantum efficiency.^{17,102} Moreover, because of the higher radiative rate, the excited-state lifetime is reduced with a resulting increase in photo-stability. Enhancement and quenching of emission (or absorption) of a molecule or a molecular aggregate, due to plasmonic effects by a close NP, is well understood by the coherent sum of the external field effects (exciting both the molecule and the NP) and those arising from the induced field, generated as a response to the external perturbation^{30,31}. It has been experimentally shown that the same strategy applied to organic dyes can also be exploited to enhance light-harvesting (LH) properties of natural photosynthetic systems.⁸⁹ In particular, the LH efficiency can be drastically enhanced by tuning the plasmon frequency of the constituent plasmonic particles to the maximal photon flux of sunlight.^{105,106} Besides, using plasmonic NPs is a promising way to control excitons in LH complexes:¹⁰⁷ indeed, in supramolecular aggregates light can be absorbed collectively by many chromophores giving rise to molecular excitons, i.e. delocalized excited states comprising a superposition of excitations at the different molecular sites. The state coherences are then used to collect light and transfer the excitation energy through space up to the reaction centers, where charge separation occurs.¹⁰⁸ The ability to control excitons in space and time is a priority

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

needed both for our understanding of the natural photosynthetic process at molecular level and for an optimal development of the exciton-based nanotechnology, which aims to supplant traditional electronics.⁹⁰ A quantitative modeling machinery is therefore necessary to achieve a complete molecular picture of these processes. The whole absorbing complex is too large to be tackled by a single electronic-structure calculation, hence a multiscale approach is required.^{6,109} In this context, a protocol has been recently developed^{57,58}:

- The supramolecular system composed of N_{sites} single chromophores (or equivalent elementary components) is described by an excitonic approximation, where the Hamiltonian

$$\hat{H}_{exc} = \sum_j^{N_{sites}} \varepsilon_j |j\rangle\langle j| + \sum_{j \neq k}^{N_{sites}} V_{jk} |j\rangle\langle k| \quad (8)$$

includes excitation energies (ε_j , usually computed at QM level) of the single chromophore j , the corresponding localized wave function $|j\rangle$ and the mutual interactions (V_{jk}). This last term is often divided in Coulomb and short-range interactions, the latter being typically negligible because of the exponential decay with distance. The Coulomb term can be directly calculated from the transition densities.^{110,111} Diagonalization of the excitonic Hamiltonian of Eq. (8) provides the excitonic energies and the adiabatic (A) description of the QM system:

$$|\Psi_A\rangle = \sum_j C_j^A |j\rangle. \quad (9)$$

The excitonic picture can be extended to include charge-transfer (CT) states. To this aim, the chromophoric units describing the CT process (such as a molecular dimer or a trimer) are defined. The excited-state calculation is performed on the basis of such CT units and a diabaticization approach is applied to recover the pure (or diabatic) locally excited and CT states and with the corresponding couplings.^{112,113} The relative energy of local and CT states is strongly affected by the presence of a polarizable embedding.^{109,113–115}

- The electrostatic and polarization effects of the protein scaffold are taken into account by a polarizable embedding scheme.¹¹⁶ QM/MM methods are the most suited to represent a complex and inhomogeneous system as a protein. The most common formulation of QM/MM methods assumes a direct interaction between the QM and the classical

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

FIG. 4. Schematic representation of the biohybrid systems involving gold nanorods and the natural photosynthetic systems: FMO (left) and LH2 (right). Figures adapted with permission from ref. 57 and 58. Copyright (2015) and (2016) American Chemical Society.

parts only through electrostatics, in which the classical atoms are represented as fixed point charges. This electrostatic embedding formulation of QM/MM methods has been extended to include mutual polarization effects, i.e. QM/MMpol between the two subsystems, through an induced dipole formulation. Within this framework, the classical atoms are described as fixed point charges (or fixed multipolar distributions) and characterized by an isotropic static polarizability: each classical particle becomes a polarizable site that responds to the field due to the QM part by generating an atomic induced dipole that polarize back the QM part, till self consistency.

- The interactions with the metal NP can be treated by classical electrodynamics and modeled by a continuum approach, as explained in Section II.

This three-layer multiscale approach (QM/MMPol/continuum), involving an atomistic and a continuum model at the same time, has been used to study plasmonic effects on the light-harvesting properties of natural photosynthetic systems, such as the Fenna-Matthews-Olson (FMO) complex⁵⁷ and the LH2 complex from photosynthetic purple bacteria *Rhodospseudomonas acidophila*, in presence of gold NPs of different shape, dimensions and configurations (Fig.4).^{58,59} In both cases, the QM part has been described by the excitonic method implemented in a TDDFT fashion.¹¹⁷ In the analyzed FMO-gold NP devices analyzed, high fluorescence enhancements were observed for different setups.⁵⁷ Enhancements of up to 2 orders of magnitude were obtained upon irradiation of the intermediate excited states of the protein, which showed stronger absorption enhancements because of their better alignment with the metal aggregates. Orientation effects seem to be crucial:

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

amplifications of up to a factor of 300 were observed for the absorption process, while the radiative decay of the emitting state increased at most by a factor of 10, mostly as a result of poor alignment of the emitting state with the considered metal aggregates. As a result, for all of the simulated configurations (number of spheres and aspect ratios), absorption enhancement seems to play the crucial role in determining the overall fluorescence enhancement of the device.

On the same foot, by comparing a hierarchy of models where the excitonic units are modified (from the single bacteriochlorophyll - BChl- to the dimer) and selected couplings are switched on or off, the investigation⁵⁸ of the excitonic processes in LH2 in presence of gold nanorods (NRs) has revealed how excitons interact with plasmons to give the observed dramatic enhancement in the fluorescence. Such an enhancement is possible only in hot-spot LH2-NR arrangements and a fundamental role is played by the orientation of LH2 with respect to the NR surface. The results also clearly indicate that, even at short LH2-NR distances, the coherent nature of the excitonic states is only slightly perturbed by the NR and their delocalization length is not significantly affected. Finally, the multiscale description has been used to justify the applicability of the classical dipolar analyses commonly used in the interpretation of the experiments. The obtained results suggested that if a fine-tuning of the coherences the dimension of the NP should be comparable to that of the LH2 complex. This was exploited in a further study⁵⁹ to demonstrate how optimally tuned tip-shaped particles can selectively excite localized regions of typically coherent systems, eventually narrowing down to probing one single pigment. The calculations showed that this can be achieved on both rings of BChls (called B800 and B850, from their absorption spectrum) of LH2. Based on those results, it was suggested that ultrafast experiments can be carried out, where the excitation is consistently prepared on a single chromophore inside the ring thanks to the nanoplasmonic tip, and the following quantum diffusion is probed by subsequent light pulses. Taking advantage of the distinctive properties of exciton systems (among which long life-times and highly efficient energy transfer) and of the ability to selectively control the pigment excitations, in terms of energy or spatial position, the metal aggregate would act as a selector or switch between energy and charge transfer pathways.

Theoretical modeling of ultrafast plasmon-assisted spectroscopies on molecules and complex systems, as FMO and LH2, would benefit from the explicit inclusion of electronic/vibrational relaxation and dephasing channels, as mentioned in Section II B. A very promising and chal-

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

lenging direction in this research field indeed focuses on the study of the possible role of genuine quantum effects in the dynamics of complex systems. The complexity of the systems under investigation called for the expertise of chemists physicists and biologists over the last years^{90,118,119}. The potential usefulness of the interplay between the coherence time of the molecular system and the intrinsic time-scales of nanoplasmons has been remarked recently.¹²⁰ Attention is drawn to the detection, use and application of quantum coherence at the nanoscale, e.g., high-resolution imaging¹²¹, coherence-tuned plasmon-based polaritons¹²¹, development of nano-optical coherence theories^{122,123}, surface-plasmon enhancement induced by coherence¹²⁴, quantum control of plasmon resonances in nanophotonics, nanoscale optical coherence sources^{123,125}. However, less is known about the role of quantum coherence in molecular plasmonics^{30,31}. Some fundamental open questions are the following: does the interplay between (de)coherence and plasmonic effects play a role in ultrafast molecular processes? Does the dephasing induced by a surrounding environment interacting with the molecular system modulate the optical properties affected by plasmons? And how the other parameters (geometry, nature, relative arrangements etc.) affect such interplay?

While these questions remain opened for large systems such as FMO and LH2, a first attempt to answer them is presented in a recent work¹³, using a multiscale ab initio approach based on the SSE⁸⁸. A time-domain QM/continuum approach with SSE (Eq. 7) has been therefore recently proposed¹³. As anticipated in Section II, the SSE framework can be coupled to the time-resolved formulation of BEM (Eq. 2) and to electronic-structure methods as DFT/TDDFT and configuration interaction (CI). The system is defined by the electronic degrees of freedom of the molecule. Time propagation is practically performed through a combination of deterministic dissipative dynamics and quantum jumps^{87,94,95}. Interaction channels by means of the \hat{S}_q operators of Eq. 7 imply relaxation (spontaneous emission and nonradiative decay with times T_1) and pure electronic dephasing with time T_2 . (De)coherence can control molecular absorption in presence of a plasmonic NP: in specific conditions, a fast (electronic) dephasing generates a decoherence between external \vec{E}_{ext} and induces \vec{E}_{ind} (on NP) field effects, leading to an absorption recovery for short molecule-NP distances¹³. These effects were studied for a test system given by a LiCN molecule, a spherical silver NP for radius equal to 5 nm, a broadband δ pulse polarized tangentially to the NP surface, as a function of the distance R between the molecule and NP (upper panel of Figure 5) in Ref. 13. In that work it was found that electronic decoherence can, even

FIG. 5. Upper panel: sketch representation of the system studied in Ref. 13. Lower panel: Decoherence-mediated enhancement of molecular absorption as a function of LiCN-NP distance R . Electron dynamics of 1 ps with $T_1=1$ ps and $T_2=50$ fs, over a range of LiCN-NP distance R between 0.3 and 10 nm. Field intensity of 0.1 W/cm^2 . Population values are normalized with respect to the respective values without NP. Reproduced from [E. Coccia and S. Corni, *J. Chem. Phys.*, **151**, 044703 (2019)], with the permission of AIP Publishing.

qualitatively (i.e., enhancement vs quenching), alter the plasmon effects on the absorption of the molecule, in a way which may be detected experimentally. In the fully coherent regime, the normalized excitation rate γ_{exc}^{coh} is given by^{30,31}

$$\gamma_{exc}^{coh} \equiv \frac{\gamma_{exc}}{\gamma_{exc}^0} = \frac{|\vec{n}_\mu \cdot (\vec{E}_{ext} + \vec{E}_{ind})|^2}{|\vec{n}_\mu \cdot \vec{E}_{ext}|^2}, \quad (10)$$

where γ_{exc} and γ_{exc}^0 are defined as the molecular excitation rate in presence of NP and for the bare molecule, and \vec{n}_μ is the unit vector pointing in direction of the transition dipole moment $\vec{\mu}$. The fields can cancel each other^{11,13,16}, as in the example presented in the lower panel of Figure 5. Decoherence of the electronic state of the molecule "decouples" the contributions from \vec{E}_{ext} and \vec{E}_{ind} , which sum up incoherently regardless of the value of the relative phase:

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

$$\gamma_{exc}^{inc} \equiv \frac{|\vec{n}_\mu \cdot \vec{E}_{ext}|^2 + |\vec{n}_\mu \cdot \vec{E}_{ind}|^2}{|\vec{n}_\mu \cdot \vec{E}_{ext}|^2}. \quad (11)$$

In the extreme case of fully incoherent regime, only absorption enhancement is possible. In Ref. 13, for a value of T_2 of 50 fs, still a partial coherence was reported (see lower panel of Figure 5 (red curve in the online version)). By decreasing T_2 fs until 5 fs, a further enhancement of molecular absorption is found according to Eq. 11. Moreover, decoherence is more important at shorter distances, at which the mutual interaction between molecule and NP is stronger.

The insights provided by the application of the theory of open quantum systems (i.e., SSE) to ultrafast plasmonic spectroscopy will allow one to explore novel scientific routes, from both the computational and experimental point of view. Coherence is indeed suggested as a further element to be considered in the design of an experimental setup: plasmonic modulation of molecular absorption is strongly modified when a fast dephasing induced acts on the molecular state, possibly breaking the coherent interaction between \vec{E}_{ext} and \vec{E}_{ind} . Furthermore, the application of this computational protocol to the study of the ultrafast dynamics of HCs in plasmon-enhanced catalysis, described in Sections III C and III D, will provide novel information on the interplay between plasmon-assisted generation of HCs and quantum coherence of the state of system (molecule/molecular fragment + metallic cluster/tip/NP), answering open questions as: how the efficiency of electron injection will be affected by low or high decoherence regimes? How nonradiative relaxation will modify the fast electron transfer?

Another perspective which deserves to be mentioned is the possible role of plasmon-based mechanisms for high-harmonic generation (HHG) in atomic gases (argon, xenon), which is source of open debate among experimentalists and theoreticians^{126–129}: high-order harmonics could be generated using relatively low-intense pulses (several orders of magnitude lower than the intensities typically applied in HHG experiments), in presence of irradiated plasmonic nanotips. If the physical nature of the detected signal is still unclear, with interpretations moving from HHG to multiphoton emission, one could be also interested in studying the role of electronic dephasing on HHG spectra of atoms and molecules¹³⁰, when interacting with plasmonic nanostructures.

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

B. Quantum coupling between nanoparticles and molecules

The quantum coupling between a metal NP and a neighbouring molecule is the interaction occurring between the LSPRs of the NP and molecular transitions. When the molecule and the plasmonic field are confined in a nanometric volume and the system is driven by an external field, the excited plasmonic modes resonate with either the vibrational or the electronic transitions of the molecule. The high intensity of the plasmonic field due to the nanometric confinement allows the nanoparticle to exchange energy coherently with the molecule or a portion of it, provided that the molecular transition exhibits a strong transition dipole moment. If such coherent exchange of energy between molecule and nanoparticle occurs, and if it occurs on time scales faster than the decay channels of the system, the system enters the strong coupling regime. Namely, to achieve this condition, the plasmonic mode and the molecular exciton need to live long enough not to damp the coherent energy exchange. Upon entering the strong coupling regime, the states of the system are best described as hybrids between light and matter: the polaritons.

While the capability of strong coupling to affect chemistry has firstly been assessed by coupling many molecules with metal NPs^{69,131}, the experimental devising of a setup to achieve single-molecule strong coupling at room temperature is endorsing the idea that also single-molecule chemistry can be tailored by shaping quantum light.

The goal of theoretically describing the dynamical modification of the properties of nanocavities and molecules in strong coupling is a formidable task. The ideal model should be able to propagate a manifold of quantum modes for the cavity together with the quantum treatment of the molecule, eventually including the external field and the nonradiative events in both the molecule and the NP^{47,132–134}. The strong light-molecule Hamiltonian (\hat{H}_{SC}) in its general shape consists of three contributions:

$$\hat{H}_{SC} = \hat{H}_{mol} + \hat{H}_{cav} + \hat{H}_{int}. \quad (12)$$

Here, \hat{H}_{mol} is the (model) molecular Hamiltonian described at any level, \hat{H}_{cav} is the quantized electromagnetic field Hamiltonian and \hat{H}_{int} is the light-matter interaction.

The minimal models to treat light-molecule strong coupling are borrowed by the modeling of spontaneous emission in confined spaces in quantum optics (Figure 6a and 6b). They consist in taking a 2-level quantum emitter as \hat{H}_{mol} (Figure 6c and 6d) and couple it via a dipolar transition to a single photon mode, *i.e.* the Jaynes-Cummings model¹³⁵ either including

FIG. 6. **a)-b)**: Population dynamics of a quantum emitter in a cavity starting with photon occupation number $p = 2$ — Spontaneous emission in presence of two decay channels κ and γ , namely the cavity loss and non-radiative decay for the emitter. The dynamics of $p = 2$ in weak coupling is governed by the dissipative behaviour. **c)-d)**: Quantum-Rabi model describing the strong coupling regime. Several features in the population dynamics arise, such as a non-purely dissipative behaviour for $p = 2$, together with a transient population of the $p = 3$ subspace in the first few femtoseconds. **e)-f)**: Quantum-Rabi model for a 5-level molecule including non-adiabatic events and nuclear dynamics via Surface-Hopping^{71,72}. Together with a transiently increasing total photon number (circled markers), a richer oscillating dynamics is shown as a result of the interplay between strong coupling and non-radiative events. The realistic treatment for the molecule also provides on-the-fly information on the molecular structure allowing to track down the progress of a polaritonic chemical reaction.

counter rotating terms¹³⁶ (Rabi model) or many 2-level emitters^{137,138} (Dicke and Tavis-Cummings models). Explicitly, the Tavis-Cummings model with N_{emit} emitters provides

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

the following expressions for the terms of Eq. 12:

$$\hat{H}_{mol} = \sum_n^{N_{emit}} \omega_n \hat{\sigma}_n^\dagger \hat{\sigma}_n \quad (13)$$

$$\hat{H}_{cav} = \omega_{cav} \hat{b}^\dagger \hat{b} \quad (14)$$

$$\hat{H}_{int} = \sum_n^{N_{emit}} \left[g_n \left(\hat{\sigma}_n^\dagger \hat{b} + \hat{\sigma}_n \hat{b}^\dagger \right) \right]. \quad (15)$$

Here, ω_n and ω_{cav} are the transition frequencies of the n -th emitter and the cavity, $\hat{\sigma}^\dagger$, $\hat{\sigma}$ are the creation and annihilation operators for the molecular excitation of the n -th emitter, \hat{b}^\dagger and \hat{b} are the creation and annihilation operators for photon modes, and g_n is the coupling strength between the n -th emitter and the quantized light. The coupling term \hat{H}_{int} between each molecular excitation and the quantized light is assumed dipolar in the long-wavelength approximation. Hence, a commonly adopted explicit interaction shape makes use of the transition dipole moment of the n -th emitter $\hat{\mu}^n$ and the single-mode electric field associated to the quantized electromagnetic mode \vec{E}_{1ph} coupled to the molecule, namely:

$$\hat{H}_{int} = \sum_n^{N_{emit}} \hat{\mu}^n \cdot \vec{E}_{1ph}. \quad (16)$$

\hat{H}_{int} in Eq. 16 coincides with the interaction term of Eq. 4, with the fundamental difference arising from the description of the field, being classical in Eq. 4 and quantum in Eq. 16. Moreover, the \vec{E}_{1ph} term can originate from the external or the NP field. Indeed, the NP-molecule coupling can be computed by the direct quantization of classical plasmonic modes¹³⁹.

Thanks to their simplicity, model Hamiltonians, as the Tavis-Cummings one, are widely exploited and offer a great perspective for a new strong-coupling chemical reactivity^{47,70,140,141}, rooting the so-called polaritonic chemistry^{47,142,143}. Such approaches based on the model molecules have the great advantage of being able to quickly investigate the polaritonic processes involving large ensemble of molecules, revealing new effects like enhanced energy transfer^{144–146} or remote control of chemical reactions¹⁴⁷. However, neglecting the molecular complexity may flatten the rich polariton-assisted chemical reactivity (Figure 1e and 1f)^{148,149}.

The first challenge here is the inclusion of the molecular complexity, e.g., explicitly accounting for the electronic Hamiltonian \hat{H}_0 of Eq. 4, for transition dipole moments computed at

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

QM level, and for nuclear motion as pointed out in Section III D. Simulating polaritonic systems is currently being developed by following two main branches. The first one is to bridge quantum optics with quantum chemistry methods^{150,151} through a reformulation of the traditional quantum-chemistry tools as cavity Born-Oppenheimer¹⁵² or quantum electrodynamics DFT¹⁵³. These quantum-chemistry coupled-to-cavity quantum electrodynamics approaches are mostly advantageous to investigate the modified electronic and vibrational properties of molecules within cavities, yet they sacrifice the realistic description of the experimental setup. The second branch is oriented towards simulating the polaritonic reactivity in realistic environments. This class of methods is based on *ad hoc* developments of the non-adiabatic polaritonic dynamics approaches^{148,154} on model molecules. Namely, such methods rely on dressing the electronic states with their interaction with quantized light and, consequently, to simulate the motion of the nuclear wavepacket on the so-obtained polaritonic potential energy surfaces^{71,155,156}. The algorithms to simulate the nuclear wavepacket motion are directly borrowed by the non-adiabatic molecular dynamics techniques which are largely exploited in simulating photochemical experiments¹⁵⁷. The benefits of exploiting non-adiabatic techniques is the possibility to treat all the degrees of freedom of a system embedded in an experimentally or biologically relevant environment under strong coupling, at both single- and many-^{133,158} molecule level. Some of us recently developed⁷¹ one of these methods based on the direct-trajectories-surface hopping (DTSH) algorithm^{159,160} and applied it to the simulation of the polaritonic photochemical isomerization of azobenzene⁷². In the cited work the electronic structure of the molecule along all the degrees of freedom has been computed by a semi-empirical electronic Hamiltonian¹⁶¹ (i.e., an *ad hoc* parametrization of \hat{H}_0), specifically developed for azobenzene and its derivatives¹⁶². The QM wave function, computed at an approximate CI level¹⁶³ is then coupled to a single mode of the electromagnetic field to build the polaritonic states and the corresponding potential energy surfaces. The motion and splitting of the nuclear wavepacket on the polaritonic potential energy surfaces is treated as a swarm of independent classical trajectories via the DTSH algorithm^{159,164,165}. The forces acting on the nuclei are computed analytically at each time step^{163,165} by including the force contribution coming from the polaritonic energy. The environment mimics the nanocavity setup experimentally realized by Baumberg and collaborators¹⁹ and it is included at QM/MM level with an electrostatic embedding^{160,166,167}, while the cavity mode field is taken as a parameter. By inclusion of all the degrees of free-

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

dom, it was shown how chemical and environmental complexities can lead to alternative polaritonic pathways characterized by an enhanced photoisomerization quantum yield for the *trans-cis* azobenzene isomerization, despite only the quenching was predicted on model molecules¹⁶⁸.

Although the development of methods for strong coupling is rapidly moving to fill the gap between models and experiments, the theoretical description still falls back on several aspects. The size of the optical cavities taken into account limits the description on both the molecular and the field components. When tackling microcavities, the huge number of molecular emitters hinders the possibility to accurately describe the chemical complexity of molecules. Careful exploitation of massive parallelization strategies and High Performance Computing may be a way out to include collective effects.¹⁵⁵

On the other hand, when nanocavity realizations approach the sub-nanometric field confinement¹⁶⁹, the possibility to control chemistry on the sub-molecular scale calls for the inclusion of geometrical features arising at both the electromagnetic field and molecular level. Hybrid models tapping into quantum methods and classical electrodynamics are indeed suitable to investigate strong coupling at a sub-nanometric level^{27,139}. In particular, in Ref. 27 a QM/continuum model is applied to calculate quantized plasmon-molecule coupling strengths using TDDFT and BEM. It was shown that depending on the molecule the use of a point dipole approximation may be unsatisfactory, as found before with QM/continuum models for absorption,³⁶ SERS⁶⁰ and enhanced fluorescence.¹²

Finally, another major open issue is the strong-coupling effect in cavities on the environment embedding the molecule, as a solvent or a more complex chemical scaffold, e.g. proteins or DNA. This is still poorly explored, and would require including a quantum character for this component of the system as well.

C. Hot-carrier generation and dynamics

In the process of dephasing and decaying through electron-electron (e-e) scattering, LSPRs efficiently transfer their energy to HC carriers (electron and holes).⁷³⁻⁷⁵. In the presence of an adsorbate at the metal NP surface or of an interface with a semiconductor, the HCs can eventually be transferred to the adsorbate or to the semiconductor. In this way the LSPR energy can be exploited in catalysis¹⁷⁰⁻¹⁷², energy generation¹⁷², sensing¹⁷³⁻¹⁷⁵,

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

and for plasmon-induced phase transition and doping^{176–178}. While the study and use of HCs in catalysis is the topic of Section III D, here we focus on the description of HC generation and dynamics.

Short timescales and difficulties in controlling the environmental conditions make addressing experimentally these physical processes extremely hard. Theoretical simulations are thus strongly envisaged. However, also on the theoretical side, the accurate description of LSPR-induced HC generation, relaxation and transfer is extremely challenging. Difficulties arise from dealing with the non-equilibrium excited-state dynamics of an interacting electronic system, possibly coupled to the nuclear degrees of freedom (as pointed out in Section III D for plasmon-enhanced catalysis). Furthermore, the system is intrinsically multiscale both in time and in space: the electronic coupling at the interface requires an atomistic description of that region, whereas the plasmonic NP size ranges from ~ 10 nm to ~ 100 nm; the plasmon decays within 10 fs, but HC relaxation and thermalization may take ~ 100 fs-1 ps.¹⁷⁹ Theoretical works on this topic provide partial direct and/or indirect information on it, such as HCs energy and momentum distribution^{75,180–184}, population dynamics^{185–188}, spectra, lifetime and mean free-path^{189,190}, plasmon linewidth with respect to adsorbates¹⁹¹, excited-state reaction barriers, etc.. In these works the modeling of the system ranges from jellium^{180,182,183} to a full atomistic treatment, and within each model the interacting electronic system may be treated at different theoretical levels ranging from a free-electron models, to DFT/TDDFT^{192,193} or GW and Bethe-Salpeter equation (BSE).^{73–75,187,189,194–196} Real-time implementation of TDDFT has been recently employed to study the mechanism of plasmon-induced HC injection on a prototype metal-acceptor interface ($\text{Ag}_{147}\text{Cd}_{33}\text{Se}_{33}$)¹⁹⁷, at the interface between a TiO_2 slab and an Ag_{20} cluster¹⁹⁸, and for a CO molecule adsorbed on Ag_{147} ¹⁹⁹.

In order to further increase the size of the system and to be able to couple a realistic NP to the quantum system of interest, multiscale approaches may be used. QM/continuum models may be directly applicable for a subset of HC experimental systems, i.e., those exploiting the antenna-reactor paradigm,²⁰⁰ where the plasmonic enhancer (antenna) and the metal cluster providing the HCs (reactor) are physically distinct. For these, the metal cluster is often small²⁰¹ and the molecule plus metal cluster may be treated QM, while the antenna may be treated by classical electromagnetic modeling.

When the HCs are generated within the plasmonic system, then the limitations of the

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

QM/continuum (and in general QM/classical) models become important. In fact, no electrons are explicitly treated in models such as PCM-NP for the NP component. The grand-challenge here is to provide a multiscale model where the NP is treated with an approach computationally affordable (for NPs of tens of nm) yet accurate enough to describe electrons or holes transfer to the molecule. Embedding approaches²⁰² are natural candidates here, and have been used already to investigate HC induced photochemistry.^{203–205} The shape and the size of the entire NPs are also important, and the model should be able to include them as well. A combination of quantum mechanical embedding and classical description of the nanoparticle electromagnetic response is a possible line of development here. Such combination has been achieved at least for the ground state of a molecule on a metal cluster.²⁰⁶ Pragmatically speaking, an approach that is also worthy to be explored is the use as the QM region of the molecule plus an affordable (a few tens of atoms) portion of the metal NPs, to be coupled with the rest of the NP described classically. While for the ground-state interaction with the molecule using a sufficiently large cluster may be enough²⁰⁷, the question arises whether the optical properties of the QM+classical NP are well described. In fact, the QM cluster compared with the corresponding piece of the entire NP suffers by two main artefacts. The first artefact is given by fictitious quantum size effects, related to the confinement of the electronic wavefunctions within the cluster. These effects are appropriate for a real metal cluster, but they should not be there for the model cluster, as its electrons are actually delocalized all over the plasmonic NP. The second one is the creation of a time-dependent polarization at the boundary between the QM and the classical part of the NP upon application of an electromagnetic field, that does not exist for the real (whole) NP. How much these two effects are important, which computational strategies can be used to mitigate them and whether they can be decreased enough to obtain useful calculations are open problems to be investigated. The results obtained by Gao and Neuhauser for a Mg slab treated QM as a whole or partitioned as QM cluster+classical continuum are encouraging,⁴² as well as various reports of a reasonable similarity in local optical properties between fully QM and classical description of tens/hundreds of atoms metal clusters.^{49,208,209}

There is a further element to be discussed concerning QM/classical models applications to HCs-induced photochemistry simulations. In this framework real-time propagation of the electronic wavepacket in presence of an external electromagnetic field and of a polarizable medium^{6,210}, as a NP and/or a solvent, may be obtained solving Eqs. 3 or 7 in conjunc-

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

tion with Eq. 4. Within this methodology the dynamics of the quantum system has been treated either at the real-time TDDFT level⁸³ or using the real-time configuration interaction method²¹⁰. DFT and TDDFT for molecules at the interface with solid materials are known to provide inaccurate molecular-level vs solid band alignment. As such, while such simulations may be illustrative of the qualitative HC transfer mechanism, they may lack in quantitative accuracy. An accurate alternative to DFT/TDDFT is given by the GW/BSE approach, developed within the many-body perturbation theory. It provides a correlated description of electronic excitations, giving a picture of the electronic coupling at the molecule/NP interface with a quality higher than that of DFT/TDDFT, and comparable to high-level quantum-chemistry methods²¹¹. At the same time the GW/BSE approach is more computationally affordable than high-level quantum-chemistry approaches. A further challenge is therefore to extend time-dependent QM/classical models to GW/BSE descriptions.

D. Plasmon-enhanced catalysis

In the last decade the plasmon assisted conversion from solar to chemical energy has stimulated great interest in the scientific community^{170,171}. Besides the great potential for technological applications¹⁷⁰ the process has a multiscale (time and size) nature that involves several steps and alternative pathways, whose interplay and contribution have not fully characterized yet^{18,212}.

A comprehensive review of what has been experimentally achieved for plasmon-enhanced catalysis is beyond the scope of this Section, hence only the main features of recent literature on applications are briefly reported here. Plasmon effects in catalysis can be of fundamental help to increase the selectivity of desired reaction pathways, to reduce unwanted reaction products, and in general to make the reaction faster and more efficient. In order to accomplish that, antenna-reactor complexes have been extensively used.^{200,201,213} The idea is to couple (large) NPs with well known plasmonic activity (Au, Ag, Al etc.) with (smaller) transition-metal clusters (Pd, Pt, Fe, Ru, metal oxides etc.). Transition-metal clusters possess advantageous electronic-structure properties that make them extremely efficient in adsorbing molecules and in triggering surface chemistry. Moreover, they show favorable selectivity²⁰⁰ compared with thermal processes. Main drawback is their weak interaction

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

with light, preventing transition-metal clusters to improve their (photo)catalytic features. On the other hand, plasmonic metals are characterized by a less intense catalytic activity, but support LSPRs with very large optical cross sections. Combining plasmonic and catalytic metal NPs in close proximity to each other, forming a strongly coupled antenna-reactor complex, therefore becomes a natural and immediate solution to get the best of the two components. Indeed, the combination of plasmonic materials with catalytic metals leads to diversified surface chemistry and reactivity not achievable on single-component plasmonic NPs. Alternatively, rhodium NPs exhibit both plasmonic and photocatalytic features²¹⁴. Water splitting, reduction and oxidation reactions involving a number of moieties (CO, CO₂, alcohols, aromatic compounds, amines, aldehydes, ketones, alkenes, alkynes etc.), and polymerization reactions have been widely investigated by means of plasmon-triggered processes.^{215,216}

The first step in plasmon-enhanced catalysis is the generation of "hot" HCs (electrons and holes)⁴ in the metal arising from the dephasing of the collective charge oscillations of plasmons, as given in the previous Section. Such HCs can activate chemical reactions involving close molecules, before relaxation mechanisms start taking place (electronic pathway). If such charge transfer is not fast enough various scattering channels, lowering the HCs energy, can favor the energy transfer to nuclear vibration (nuclear pathway). Both processes contribute to the determination of the plasmonic enhancement of the reaction rates, yet the factors determining the balance between the two pathways are not clear^{217,218}. Hence, future developments in this field are expected to contribute to the clarification of the competition between electron and nuclear pathways in plasmon-assisted catalysis. A promising strategy for next developments, based on the multiscale modeling of the steps involved in the process, might focus on (i) the description of the HCs wave function, (ii) the study of the dynamics of the HCs (iii) and the energy transfer to the nuclear degrees of freedom (dof).

Modeling HCs in small metallic nanoparticles (~ 300 atoms) can be achieved via the TDDFT approach⁸² mentioned in Section II, but for larger NPs (average size of 5-25nm, ~ 30000 atoms) a simplified description is necessary. Indeed free-particle-like approaches have been shown to provide a description of HCs that is in good agreement with DFT, and a first multiscale model combining them with a classical plasmon field has been used to study the HCs generation in spherical NPs as a function of the NP size¹⁸⁰. Nevertheless modeling HCs in sizable general-shaped nanoparticles is still a challenge.

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

Continuum approaches (e.g., BEM) have been successfully applied to the description of free-particle wave functions in general-shaped confining objects²¹⁹. Plasmon-induced generation of HCs can be then simulated within a BEM framework in the approximation of describing HCs as confined free particles. This approach is fully general, and can be applied to both antenna-reactor systems and single NPs: in the former case, the antenna is classically described. In what follows, we therefore refer to a generic NP to indicate the plasmonic system generating the HCs. Generally speaking, the BEM approach allows expressing the electric field inside (and outside) the confining NP as generated from auxiliary sources localized on the (discretized) NP surface, Γ , through the electrostatic Green's function. The auxiliary sources are then obtained by solving numerically a set of BEM equations defined by the boundary conditions. The same approach can be applied to free-particle wave functions (ψ_i) because the Green's function (G_i) of the Schrödinger equation with zero or constant potential is known analytically²¹⁹ in terms of the energies E_i obtaining:

$$\psi_i(\vec{r}) = \int_{\Gamma} [u_i(\vec{s})\partial G_i(\vec{r}, \vec{s}) - \partial u_i(\vec{s})G_i(\vec{r}, \vec{s})] d\vec{s} \quad (17)$$

The auxiliary sources u_i and ∂u_i , defined on the boundary mesh, are obtained by solving the BEM equations once the energies E_i have been determined by imposing that BEM equations admit non trivial solutions²¹⁹. Two BEM problems are formulated for the ψ_i outside (zero potential) and inside (constant negative potential) the NP. The boundary conditions that define the BEM equations, from Eq. (17) with $\vec{r} \in \Gamma$, are the continuity of the wave function and its derivative on Γ . The value of the (constant) potential inside the NP is defined in order to reproduce the metal work function¹⁸⁰. BEM equations in this particular case have the form of a linear homogeneous system of equations with size equal to the number of Γ mesh points P , The higher P the better the description of high-energy states, but, as the computational cost of the best available numerical solution increases as P^3 , the solution of the BEM problems for the different states i can be trivially parallelized. The NP, here, is not only intended as a polarizable continuum medium, generating the plasmonic field in its proximity. Indeed, it is also the confining domain of the HCs, that constitute the central quantum system in this multiscale model.

HCs time evolution is driven primarily by the electron transfer to (from) the absorbed molecule and a fast relaxation (~ 10 - 100 fs) dominated by electron-electron (e-e) scattering²²⁰. Eventually, on longer timescales, the energy can be transferred to vibrations via electron-

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

phonon coupling⁴. The competition between the fast relaxation and the electron transfer determines the dominant activation pathway. In fact the e-e scattering, decreasing the energy of HCs, can hamper the electron transfer to/from the molecule favoring the nuclear activation pathway. One way to address such issue would be the quantum propagation of the HCs wave function within the SSE framework²²⁰. In previous works HCs dynamics has been simulated in two steps: first computing the energy distribution in frequency domain¹⁸⁰ and then evolving the state populations adding relaxation channels²²⁰. In this multiscale framework one could perform a time-domain quantum dynamics, using the set of $|\psi_i\rangle$ as a basis, simulating both the generation and the relaxation processes in a single step. The SSE describing the time evolution of all HCs would have the following form:

$$i\frac{d|\Psi_S(t)\rangle}{dt} = [\hat{H}_S(t) + \hat{R}] |\Psi_S(t)\rangle, \quad (18)$$

where the general form of \hat{H}_S is given by Eq. 4 and $|\Psi_S(t)\rangle$ is the HCs wave function written as a linear combination of $|\psi_i\rangle$ with time-dependent coefficients. We stress here that being the HCs the central system \hat{H}_{pol} defines the interaction between the plasmonic field and the HCs, and \vec{E}_{ext} may also contain the time-dependent field generated by the polarized charge density of molecular species adsorbed on the nanoparticle surface. \hat{R} contains the projectors relative to the different relaxation channels weighted by the respective characteristic rates, namely, according to Eq. 7, $\hat{R} = \sum_q^R l_q(t)\hat{S}_q - \frac{i}{2} \sum_q^R \hat{S}_q^\dagger \hat{S}_q$, with q running over the number R of relaxation channels and \hat{S}_q pure relaxation operators. One could start by only including the e-e relaxation channel because the timescales of the vibrational couplings are at least one order of magnitude longer. In Section III A, dephasing channels have been also taken into account. A first estimation of the balance between the nuclear and the electron energy pathways would be obtained by comparing the time evolution of the population of HCs at an energy that is higher or equal to the one of the molecular acceptor state, with the electron-transfer rates to molecular states. In fact only the HCs at energies higher or equal to the molecular acceptor state can be transferred. Transfer rates could be estimated using standard literature approaches (e.g. Marcus theory) with a molecule adsorbed on a periodic surface or a molecule-NP smaller clusters at the DFT level of theory, or similar approaches. We underline that in principle the HC injection in molecular empty states could be described by the SSE dynamics but this would require the computation of mixed integrals between molecular and HCs states.

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

The final step of the process, for both the electronic and nuclear energy pathways, is the energy transfer to the nuclear dof. Concerning the electronic pathway, the relaxation of the electronic excited (and charged) state of the molecule might be modeled, for simple reactions, via Ehrenfest dynamics²²¹ of the molecular dof polarized by the NP described at the classical level⁸³.

On the nuclear pathway side, the energy transfer from the NP to the molecule(s) might be modeled via atomistic classical molecular-dynamics simulations allowing the exploration the plasmon thermal effect on the free energy barrier of even more complex reactions, including solvent and surface effects, via enhanced sampling techniques. The thermal activation could involve the solvent and molecular species not directly chemi- or physisorbed on the NP surface²²². The energy transfer to vibrations can be simulated via multiple thermostats approaches²²³, and the free-energy barriers computed via metadynamics²²⁴ and umbrella sampling²²⁵. A new topology-based collective variable scheme²²⁶, might be used to describe multi-step, solvent- or surface-assisted reactions where the reaction coordinate is other than trivial. The outcomes of such a multiscale approach would be the setup of the characterization of the competition between nuclear and electronic energy pathways for plasmon-assisted catalysis in terms of NP shape, size and nature, and the description of the plasmon effect on free-energy barriers and reaction mechanisms of high-interest chemical reactions including solvent and surface effects. Further developments would concern the inclusion of electron-phonon couplings^{227,228}, and the description of more complex systems, i.e. adding a semiconductor support or treating coated NPs²¹².

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this Perspective we have discussed some of the open challenges in molecular plasmonics that can be theoretically addressed by a combination of different approaches defining efficient and accurate hybrid models. These integrated methods are based on QM/continuum models, and coupled to a time propagation. Fast and ultrafast dynamics of HCs and nuclei therefore become (or will become in the next future) accessible to a detailed investigation of the nature of the light-matter interaction at the nanoscale. The outlook reported here covers a selected range of physical phenomena, and proposes a direct connection between various areas of the scientific community, both from the theoretical and experimental side. The development of

Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

theoretical models and computational techniques is indeed inspired by a constant dialogue with experimental evidences and breakthroughs in nanophotonics, with the final goal of a joint approach for the description, interpretation and prediction of physical processes of interest.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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Models for molecular nanoplasmonics

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